

MULTI-INDEX ASSESSMENT OF LONG-TERM (2001–2021) DROUGHT DYNAMICS: A CASE STUDY FROM BARIND TRACT OF BANGLADESH

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The Barind Tract, one of the most drought-prone and climatically vulnerable regions of Bangladesh, faces persistent moisture stress due to limited rainfall, high temperatures, and restricted groundwater availability. Drought is a recurring climate hazard that significantly affects agricultural productivity and water resources nationwide. This study analyzes multi-year drought patterns from 2001 to 2021 using multiple drought indices, including the Vegetation Condition Index (VCI), Temperature Condition Index (TCI), Precipitation Concentration Index (PCI), Standardized Moisture Condition Index (SMCI), and Integrated Drought Index (IDI) and Agro-meteorological Drought Index (AIDI). The indices exhibit substantial interannual variability: AIDI ranged from 17.4 in 2006 to 82.6 in 2020, and VCI ranged from 7.3 in 2001 to 89.3 in 2019, reflecting pronounced shifts in vegetation stress. Extreme drought events were evident in 2006, 2009, and 2014, marked by exceptionally low moisture-related indices (SMCI values of 21.35 in 2006 and 2.51 in 2014) and corresponding increases in precipitation irregularity. In contrast, 2017–2020 showed comparatively favorable hydro-meteorological conditions, with high VCI (up to 89.3 in 2019) and elevated SMCI values. Correlation analysis confirmed that VCI and SMCI are strong indicators of vegetation and soil moisture responses to drought, while PCI and TCI highlight meteorological and thermal anomalies. These findings enhance the understanding of long-term drought dynamics in the region and provide valuable insights for drought monitoring, early warning systems, and adaptive agricultural planning.

Keywords: Drought, Barind Tract, Vegetation Condition Index (VCI), Agro-Meteorological Drought Index (AIDI), and Agricultural Planning